

Simultaneous High-resolution LIF Measurements of Dissolved Gas Concentration Fields and Measurements of Wave Slope at a Wavy Free Water Surface with Wind-induced Turbulence

Alexandra Herzog^{1,2}, Felix Friedl^{1,2}, Bernd Jähne^{1,2}

1: Institute of Environmental Physics, The University of Heidelberg, Germany

2: Heidelberg Collaboratory for Image Processing at the Interdisciplinary Center for Scientific Computing, University of Heidelberg, Germany, {Alexandra.Herzog, Felix.Friedl, Bernd.Jaehne}@iwr.uni-heidelberg.de

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1. Description of Problem

The exchange of gases and volatile species with moderate solubility between ocean and atmosphere is controlled by the aqueous mass boundary layer. The complex interplay between shear-induced turbulence and short nonlinear wind waves in this layer is only marginally understood. Therefore, the measurement of concentration fields plays an important role.

However, almost all experimental investigations are limited to grid or jet stirred tanks with a flat water surface (Tsumori et al., 2007, Herlina et al., 2008, Schulz et al., 2009, Asher et al., 2009). Experimental investigations under wind-induced turbulence with a wavy water surface are rare. Münsterer et al., 1998, studied only mean vertical concentration profiles and gas transfer rates. Only Walker et al., 2008 investigated the fluctuations of the concentration fields under wind-induced turbulence in combination with mechanically generated waves.

All previous investigators used laser-induced fluorescence (LIF) techniques for visualizing water-sided gas concentration fields. Wind-generated surface roughness is a severe experimental problem for LIF measurements as the illuminating laser light sheet is subjected to focusing and defocusing effects caused by light refraction at the varying curvature of the water surface. Leaving these effects uncorrected leads to wrong estimates of gas concentration. Therefore, simultaneous measurement of local gas concentration and local surface orientation is required in turbulence studies at rough water surfaces.

2. Method

In this study we present a significantly improved LIF technique that is suitable for high-resolution measurements of dissolved gas concentration fields in a vertical plane oriented in wind-direction close to a wavy water surface in wind/wave facilities. Our approach extends the earlier work of Münsterer et al. (1998), who used an acid gas (HCl) and a fluorescent pH indicator to visualize the concentration fields of dissolved gases in water.

3. Advancement

In the present study on wind-induced turbulence, a LIF measurement setup is introduced with three significant improvements:

Firstly, the fluorescent pH-indicator 8-hydroxypyrene-1,3,6-trisulfonic acid trisodium salt (HPTS) is used instead of fluorescein. HPTS offers a larger Stokes-shift of 53 nm and a higher photo stability as compared to fluorescein, (Falkenroth et al., 2006).

Secondly, the optical resolution is improved by an optimized setup. Aberrations are minimized by observing the vertical illuminated sheet through a titled side window with the optical axis perpendicular to this window in a Scheimpflug arrangement (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Cross section of the linear flume together with sketch of Scheimpflug-Setup of the imaging system of CCD-camera and tilted observation window. Besides the desired fluorescing plane the imaged area contains also part of the total reflection of the fluorescing plane at the air-water interface (upper part of the images in Figure 2).

Thirdly, the intensity of the vertical light-sheet - illuminating from above - is varied randomly in horizontal direction (Fig. 2) to achieve a non-uniform light sheet. In this way, the horizontal position is coded as a varying structure. These vertically oriented patterns allow to determine the along-wind slope of the short wind waves.

Figure 2: Raw data LIF-image sections; imaged area 35 x 14 mm, pixel resolution 25 micrometer; segmented water surface marked with white-dashed line; the wind blows from right to left, fetch 1.6 m. The distorted image above the water surface is caused by total reflection at the wavy water surface (see Figure 1 for setup).

Top: Image of injection-event at a wind speed of 3 m/s with flat interface.

Middle: Image of injection-event at a wind speed of 5 m/s.

Bottom: Image at a wind speed of 6m/s with steep capillary waves, which lead to strong distortions of the illuminated light sheet

The angle of the along-wind wave slope α is related to the inclination angle γ of the oriented structure as

$$\begin{aligned}\tan \alpha &= \frac{n_w \tan \gamma}{n_w - (1 + \tan^2 \gamma)^{1/2}} \\ &= 4 \tan \gamma + O(\tan^3 \gamma) \quad \text{with } n_w \approx \frac{4}{3}\end{aligned}$$

(Jähne et al., 1994, n_w is the index of refraction of water).

It is also possible to correct for the intensity variations resulting from the above mentioned focusing and defocusing effects. Figure 2 indicates that these distortions are not significant close to the water interface with distances up to about ten times the thickness of the thin mass boundary layer, which is important for determination of fluctuations within the mass boundary layer. Gas concentration gained

from LIF profiles in greater depth, however, have to be corrected for these effects.

Therefore the additional evaluation of the surface slope, from LIF raw data enables the extraction of reliable gas concentration fields close to the water surface even at a wavy surface with high surface curvature.

A series of measurements was performed in a small linear wind/wave tunnel, which has been constructed for these measurements with the previously described tilted observation windows. The water segment is 4 m long, 32 cm wide and 9 cm deep. It has a gas-tight closed air circulation with a total air volume of 3 m³ and is coated with PTFE for usage of highly reactive species.

Measurements were carried out with wind speeds ranging from 1 to 8 m/s and at fetches between 0.4 and 2.0 m. The image sequences were recorded with up to 67 frames per second and a resolution of 1400 x 1024 pixels, corresponding to a spatial resolution of 25 μ m/pixel.

Currently, a detailed analysis of the image sequences is underway. At the symposium we will show corrected concentration fields and the extracted along-wind wave slope data and analyze the spatio-temporal variations of the thickness of the mass boundary layer and thus the instantaneous local gas transfer rate.

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